

We report here briefly our findings on the cobalt (II) chelate of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime. It is orange-red in colour and is formulated as HCoL_3 . It is paramagnetic and its magnetic moment at room temperature is found to be 1.86 B.M. It shows the presence of one unpaired electron and hence of bivalent cobalt. The octahedral crystal field is considered to be strong leading to the spin-pairing of d-electrons in cobalt (II). The visible absorption spectrum of the chelate has a d-d band at 17000 cm^{-1} . The band is attributed to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. in the strong octahedral crystal field. The crystal field splitting (Δ) is suggested to be 17000 cm^{-1} . Usually, the spin-pairing energy (P) for cobalt (II) in its weak octahedral complexes is given as $\sim 22500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Δ as $\sim 10000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Since p will be higher than Δ , no spin-pairing should be observed in such complexes. We find that covalent bonding, as evidenced by the determination of β , is present to a considerable extent in the chelate. Hence spin-pairing energy which can be evaluated as $4B+4C$ (where B and C are Racah parameters) has been found to have a low value of 12240 cm^{-1} . It indicates favourable condition ($\Delta > p$) for spin-pairing in the chelate. Further, from the comparative studies of other chelates, it is considered likely that pi-bonding between metal and ligand exists. It would involve t_{2g} electrons of cobalt (II) leading to the delocalisation of these electrons (i.e., apparently modifying the bivalent nature of cobalt).

Reference

1. P. L. PATHAK and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1972, 49, 745.

Outer Sphere Association in Tris(biguanide) Cobalt (III) Salts

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TRIS(BIGUANIDE) cobalt (III) cation has a high inner sphere formation constant¹ ($K = 10^{54}$). The complex shows asymmetric transformation of the second order during resolution². Furthermore the complex also shows interesting kinetics and mechanistic behaviour during acid hydrolysis³. We now report the outer sphere association constants of the salts $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$ (BigH = biguanide; X = Cl, Br, I, and $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$)

The association constants were obtained from a study of the conductance of the pure salts with dilution in aqueous medium at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. An approximate value of Λ^0 was obtained by plotting the experimental Λ against $\sqrt{c}$. The approximate

Λ^0 was fitted into Onsager's conductivity equation⁴ and 'b' value was thus obtained. From a plot of $\Lambda + b\sqrt{c}$ against c an accurate value of the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution, Λ^0 (Onsager), was obtained whence Λ^0_i , the limiting conductivity of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$, was available. The experimental conductivity plots lie below the Onsager plots, which is taken to mean that outer sphere association occurs in these salts. Table 1, gives the values of Λ^0 , Λ^0 (Onsager) and Λ^0_i for the chloride, bromide and the iodide salts of the complex cation.

Assuming the ion-pair to be $\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2\text{X}]\text{X}_2$ (X = Cl, Br, I), Onsager equations for the 3:1 valent salt ($[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$) and for the 2:1 salt (the ion-pair) have been written, and association constants for the equilibrium

have been calculated following Jenkins and Monk⁵. For the sulphate salt Λ^0 (Onsager) was obtained by adding 80.00 for the sulphate ion to the mean limiting cation conductivity derived from the chloride, bromide and iodide salts. The outer sphere association constants are given in Table 2. Comparison of these constants with those of $\{[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ and $\{[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{X}\}^{2+}$ (en = ethylenediamine; X = Cl, Br, I, SO_4) shows that, the constants increase in the usual order $\text{I}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE DATA OF $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{X}_3$ (X = Cl, Br, I) IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$

Complex salt	Approximate Λ^0	Onsager Λ^0	Λ^0_i (for the cation)	Mean Λ^0_i
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	146.00	143.88	67.54	
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Br}_3$	148.00	147.00	68.60	68.08
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{I}_3$	145.00	144.90	68.10	

TABLE 2—OUTER SPHERE ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3\text{X}_2]\text{X}_2$

Ion-pair	Association constant
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{Cl}]\}^{2+}$	55
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{Br}]\}^{2+}$	33
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3, \text{I}]\}^{2+}$	22
$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{SO}_4)\}^{2+}$	16×10^2

From a knowledge of the limiting conductivity of the ion, the ionic radius has been calculated from Stoke's law (Table 3). Expectedly $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ (1.03 Å) is substantially bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ (2.77 Å)⁶ and is only slightly bigger than $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ (3.68 Å)⁶. A smaller value compared to the size⁶

of $[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3]^{3+}$ (pn = propylenediamine) is somewhat disturbing. The association constants were also utilised to determine the radii of the ion-pairs from Bjerrum equation. Unfortunately the Bjerrum distances (Table 3) did not agree well with those obtained from the sum of the anion radii and the cation radii, both being obtained from Stoke's law. However, such discrepancies have also been noted by Jenkins and Monk⁵.

TABLE 3—APPROXIMATE RADII OF $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ AND ION-PAIRS

Cation/anion	Radius from Stoke's law a(A)	Ion pair	Radius from Stoke's law a(A)	Radius from Bjerrum equation a(A)
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$	4.03			
Cl^-	1.20	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}\}^{2+}$	5.23	4.28
Br^-	1.18	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Br}\}^{2+}$	5.21	6.11
I^-	1.19	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{I}\}^{2+}$	5.22	7.38
SO_4^{--}	2.29	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{SO}_4\}^+$	6.32	5.03

We have been investigating a number of other inert cobalt (III) complexes namely $[\text{Co}(\text{PhBigH})_3]^{3+}$ (PhBigH = phenylbiguanide), $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ (AA = dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline). Details of these studies will be published in due course.

References

1. A. K. DE, N. N. GHOSH and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 493.
2. P. RAY and N. K. DUTT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 81.
3. D. BANERJEA and B. CHAKRAVARTY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1233.
4. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, *Electrolyte Solutions*, 2nd Ed. Butterworths, London, 1968.
5. I. L. JENKINS and C. B. MONK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 68.

Dipterocarpol from Wood Extractives of Dipterocarpaceae

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SEVERAL *Dipterocarpaceae* species grow in Bangladesh. Dipterocarpol has been isolated directly from the petroleum extract of the weed of *D. turbinatus*, a species available here in abundance. It has been identified as hydroxydammarone-II on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p., infrared absorption and of its conversion to dammarenediol-II. Earlier it was isolated from the balsams¹⁻³ and the hydrolytic

products of the weed extractives⁴ of some *Dipterocarpaceae* species and shown identical with hydroxydammarone-II, a tetracyclic triterpene derivative, isolated from dammar,^{5,6} a group of natural resins originating from the trees of *Dipterocarpaceae* family.

Experimental

Dried powdered weed of *D. turbinatus* was extracted with petroleum ether (40°–60°) at room temperature for 48 hrs; the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure, when a yellowish gummy mass (0.61%) deposited. On standing for a couple of days a crystalline solid appeared in the gum. On careful washing with light petroleum ether, gummy portion dissolved preferentially leaving behind a white material which afforded from light petroleum ether crystals, m.p. 126°–128°, resolidified, and then m.p., 132°–134°. The crystals (500 mg.) were chromatographed on alumina in petroleum ether (40°–60°) and eluted first with light petroleum ether, then with benzene and finally with methanol. Eluates from petroleum ether gave a trace of gum, and from methanol yielded crystalline product (415 mg.) which, on further crystallisations from methanol appeared as plates, m.p. 127°–128° (resolidified and then m.p. 135°–136°); $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +67.08$ (c. 1.05 in CHCl_3); infrared bands at 3570, 1695, 1440 and 1375 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 81.3; H, 11.2%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.4; H, 11.4%). [For dipterocarpol Cosserat³ records m.p. 127° (resolidifies and then m.p. 132°–134°); $[\alpha]_D = +65^\circ$; Mclean⁴ gives m.p. 132°–134°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +67^\circ$ (c. 1.09 in CHCl_3). It gave the same colour reactions as Hydroxydammarone-II as recorded by Mills⁵. Its semicarbazone melted at 204°–206° (Crabbe⁷ gives m.p. 206°–207; Mclean⁴ records m.p. 203°–205°).

Reduction of dipterocarpol: Dipterocarpol (200 mg) was reduced in methanol (75 ml) with sodium (4 g.), the product isolated and chromatographed over alumina in benzene. Benzene-ether (19:1) elute gave a product which on crystallisation twice from methanol appeared as crystals of dammarenediol (75 mg), m.p. 130°–132° (recorded⁵ m.p. 130°–132°).

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References

1. L. VAN ITALLIE, *Arch. Pharm.* 1912, **250**, 204.
2. D. H. GOODSON, F. E. KING and T. J. KING, *Chem. & Ind.* 1956, 190.
3. L. COSSEBAT, G. OURISSON and T. TAKAHASHI, *Chem & Ind.* 1956, 190.
4. J. MCLEAN and W. E. WATTS, *J. Org. Chem.* 1960, **25**, 1263.
5. J. S. MILLS and A. E. A. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1955, 3132.
6. J. S. MILLS, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1956, 2196.
7. P. Crabbe, G. OURISSON and TAKAHASHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, **3**, 279.